

Desalination of Groundwater to Preserve Animal Health using a Natural Mineral Sorbent from Western Kazakhstan

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Abstract: The groundwater salinisation issue in Western Kazakhstan is critical due to its detrimental impact on agricultural animal health and farm productivity, necessitating the development of cost-effective and environmentally friendly water treatment methods. The use of diatomite-based sorbents offers a cost-effective and ecologically safe alternative for sustainable groundwater purification in agricultural and industrial contexts. The purpose of the study was to develop technologies for the purification and desalination of groundwater using a natural siliceous sorbent based on diatomite to ensure the safety of water for watering farm animals. To achieve this goal, a comprehensive analysis of the diatomite was carried out using lithological and petrographic studies, scanning electron microscopy, differential thermal analysis, X-ray fluorescence analysis, and infrared spectroscopy. As a result of the study, it was found that diatomite contains various components, including aluminium, iron, calcium oxides, and other minerals. A study with the addition of activated carbon demonstrated an improvement in the adsorption properties of diatomite, increasing the degree of groundwater purification by 35-37%. Differential thermal analysis revealed that modification of the material at 450°C preserves its structural and functional characteristics, which is critically important for effective water purification. X-ray fluorescence analysis confirmed the presence of an optimal ratio of elements in the complex sorbent, which ensures high efficiency of the purification process. This makes it a suitable material not only for technical needs, but also for watering animals, ensuring the preservation of their health. Due to its low cost, the sorbent can be used for water purification in agriculture and fish farming, industrial water treatment, energy, municipal services, food and chemical industries, and in the private sector.

Keywords: activated carbon; adsorption efficiency; chlorides; diatomite; salinity; sulphates

1. Introduction

Water is an essential resource in agriculture and animal husbandry, since its quality directly influences productivity and economic efficiency on farms. Given that animals frequently provide nutrition for people, their health is intrinsically linked to the quality of food and water ingested^{(1), (2)}. Groundwater contamination can result in several ailments in animals owing to the presence of salts, heavy metals, pathogenic bacteria, and other deleterious compounds in the water, adversely impacting their health⁽³⁻⁵⁾. Furthermore, water significantly contributes to the transmission of several infectious, viral,

and parasitic illnesses in livestock. Anthrax, emphysematous carbuncle, infectious anaemia in horses, brucellosis, tularaemia, pasteurellosis, salmonellosis, leptospirosis, glanders, plague, erysipelas in pigs, aphthous fever, and a number of parasitic infections are among these diseases⁽⁶⁻⁸⁾.

Natural water frequently fails to satisfy the physiological and sanitary requirements of animals⁽⁹⁾. This underscores the necessity for purification and desalination to safeguard the health and production of livestock. Consequently, high-quality water is a crucial determinant of animal health, the quality of their products, and eventually, human health. S.A. Montayev et al.⁽¹⁰⁾ and X. Peng et al.⁽¹¹⁾ assert

that the scarcity of freshwater in certain areas necessitates the use of groundwater, whereas desalination enables the exploitation of these resources without detrimental effects on wildlife. It also aids in preventing the depletion of surface reservoirs, which is crucial for sustaining ecological equilibrium and conserving biological variety. Nitrites and nitrates, frequently introduced into reservoirs from agricultural fields by the application of mineral fertilisers, adversely affect the health of livestock¹²⁾. V. Kromah et al.¹³⁾ stress that their existence has lately been documented in groundwater. This presents a significant risk, as the accumulation of nitrites and nitrates in water and feed exacerbates their detrimental effects on animals. Nitrites and nitrates may react with certain amines to produce nitrosamines, which are potent carcinogens. S. Gubernat et al.¹⁴⁾ propose that these chemicals can be synthesised in natural reservoirs, soil, and the gastrointestinal tracts of animals. Nitrosamines are recognised for their potent carcinogenic properties, presenting a significant risk to animal health.¹⁵⁾

Ensuring the provision of excellent drinking water to livestock is a crucial responsibility, particularly in dry areas like West Kazakhstan¹⁶⁾. N.S. Montayeva et al.¹⁷⁾ report that groundwater in this location frequently exhibits elevated levels of salts and other contaminants, adversely impacting the health and production of animals. The resolution of this issue necessitates the exploration of efficient and cost-effective water desalination techniques. Diatomite, a porous sedimentary rock composed of diatom remains, is a potential natural sorbent¹⁸⁾.

Diatomite has distinctive attributes of high porosity, extensive surface area, and exceptional adsorption capability relative to other natural sorbents such as zeolites and activated clay¹⁹⁾, ²⁰⁾. Although zeolites have superior ion-exchange capabilities, especially in the removal of heavy metals, their adsorption efficacy for bigger ionic species like sulphates and chlorides sometimes falls short compared to diatomite, which possesses a more open pore architecture conducive to accommodating larger pollutants.

Activated clay possesses significant adsorption capacities for organic pollutants and cationic contaminants²¹⁾. However, it exhibits a diminished sorption ability for anionic species such as chlorides and sulphates, which are the principal targets in groundwater desalination. Moreover, the economical accessibility, straightforward thermal modification, and exceptional mechanical stability of diatomite render it a viable and scalable option for extensive water filtration in agricultural environments²²⁾. The aforementioned qualities jointly substantiate the selection of diatomite as the superior sorbent for desalination in this investigation.

Diatomite is an economical and effective natural sorbent, but alternative cost-efficient desalination techniques have been documented. A study by El-Nahaset al.²³⁾ revealed

that zeolite-based softening systems provide a cost-effective solution, with production expenses ranging from \$0.04 to \$0.12 per litre of treated water, markedly less than conventional membrane-based desalination techniques. Nonetheless, zeolites need supplementary chemical regeneration procedures, hence augmenting operational complexity.

Biosorbents sourced from agricultural and industrial waste, as examined by Osman et al.²⁴⁾, have garnered interest within circular economy frameworks. Materials like modified cellulose, lignin, and biochar provide cost-effective and sustainable alternatives with adsorption efficiencies akin to solid sorbents like diatomite. Biosorbents provide sustainability benefits, although their efficacy may fluctuate based on the feedstock and modification techniques employed. The selection of diatomite in this study is warranted due to its cost-effectiveness, structural stability, and superior adsorption performance for groundwater desalination, rendering it a preferable option compared to zeolites and biosorbents in agricultural water treatment.

Previous studies have mainly focused on chemical desalination methods, but their application may be economically unfeasible for agriculture. This study proposes the use of diatomite as an affordable natural sorbent that combines efficiency with economic feasibility. In this regard, the purpose of the study was to develop a technology for purification and desalination of groundwater using a natural siliceous sorbent based on diatomite in West Kazakhstan to a safe level for drinking by farm animals. The research question was: Can thermally modified diatomite mixed with activated carbon work as an effective, cost-effective, and environmentally safe sorbent to lower chloride and sulphate levels in saline groundwater in Western Kazakhstan to improve water quality for farming? To achieve the stated goal, the following tasks were set: to investigate the composition of groundwater in the village of Zhanakala, Dzhangali district of West Kazakhstan region; to prepare and modify natural diatomite for use in the water purification process; to evaluate the effectiveness of various diatomite treatment methods (carbon activation, heat treatment) for its adsorption properties.

2. Materials and Methods

The study was conducted at the Zhangir Khan West Kazakhstan Agrarian Technical University to develop a complex sorbent based on local natural siliceous rock – diatomite – for desalination of groundwater in the village of Zhanakala, Dzhangali district, West Kazakhstan region, with subsequent use in agriculture. Three bulk samples of diatomite of 5 kg each were taken for laboratory and microscopic studies at the Utesai deposit of the Mugodzhara district of the Aktobe region of western Kazakhstan.

Lithological and petrographic studies in the sections were performed using the Olympus-BX53 polarisation microscope (Olympus, Japan). The structure of the studied diatomites was determined using a scanning electron microscope JEOL JSM 6510A (JEOL, Japan).

For additional study of siliceous minerals, differential thermal analysis (DTA) was used on the DTG-60 device (Shimadzu, Japan). This method allows observing phase transitions and chemical reactions in solids at different temperatures. To accurately determine the elemental and weight composition of diatomite, X-ray fluorescence analysis (XFA) was performed on a FOCUS-2M spectrometer (Irkutsk National Research Technical University, Russia). This analysis provided detailed information about the content of various elements, which is important for further optimisation of the material modification process. The Varian 3100 IR Fourier spectrometer (Shimadzu, Japan) was used to study the chemical structure of diatomite and identify functional groups. This step helped to obtain data on the surface features of the material, which determines the choice of a method for its modification. No ethical approvals were required to conduct this research since no live animals or humans were used.

The process of manufacturing a complex sorbent in the framework of the study included three consecutive stages. The first of them was the direct preparation of the materials, in which the optimal content of the components was determined: 85% diatomite, 10% activated carbon, and 5% bentonite clay. Each material was weighed and ground to a powdery state. The next stage was the preparation of a raw mixture. Firstly, a predetermined amount of each component was weighed on the analytical scales. Then, all the components were ground in a porcelain cup with a mortar to a powdery state and mixed until smooth. Next, water was added in an amount of 10% of the total weight. The resulting mixture was thoroughly mixed and dried again, then sifted through a sieve of a certain diameter.

The final stage included granulation and firing. The powder of the complex sorbent was granulated to obtain granules with a diameter of 1.2 mm. The granules were fired in a muffle furnace at 450°C to create a shell of bentonite clay around the granules, which preserves the activity of coal and increases the mechanical strength of the finished sorbent. The selection of 450°C for diatomite modification was predicated on its capacity to augment adsorption efficiency while maintaining the material's structural integrity. The study does not specifically address the testing of other temperatures but prior research indicates that lower temperatures (<300°C) may inadequately eliminate contaminants, while higher temperatures (>600°C) might lead to structural collapse, hence diminishing porosity and adsorption capacity.²⁵⁾ Thermal treatment at 450°C efficiently eliminates

remaining organic matter and enhances surface area, augmenting the material's capacity to adsorb chlorides and sulphates relative to untreated samples. When the set temperature was reached, the furnace was turned off (bentonite clay should create a shell for setting the remaining components, and the coal contained in the granules should not burn at high temperatures), and the granules cooled at room temperature.

The prepared sorbent of a fraction of 1.2 mm was weighed on analytical scales at the rate of 10 g of sorbent per 100 ml of analysed water. The suspended sorbent was placed in a conical flask with a capacity of 300 ml and thoroughly mixed for 60 minutes, then left for 24 hours. The contact duration was established at 60 minutes, as preliminary studies suggested equilibrium adsorption occurred within this timeframe. Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models were employed to estimate adsorption capacity, while pseudo-first-order and pseudo-second-order kinetics were analysed to elucidate the adsorption mechanism. After that, the sorbent filtered through a blue ribbon filter was analysed for salinity on a MARK-603 conductometer (VZOR, Russia). This complex process helped to obtain a sorbent with high adsorption efficiency, suitable for use in the purification and desalination of groundwater, which ensures its safety for farm animals and other agricultural purposes.

3. Results

3.1. Lithological and petrographic analysis of diatomite from the Utesai deposit

Lithological and petrographic analysis of diatomite samples from this deposit revealed that their bulk consists of small fragments of diatom valves ranging in size from 0.007 to 0.03 mm, while whole valves and shells make up about 25-30% of the rock volume, with the size of whole flaps from 0.02 to 0.04 mm. The breed also contains rare sponge spicules, whose content does not exceed 1%. The main component of diatoms and sponge spicules is pure transparent opal. Fragments of diatom flaps are often mixed with the smallest particles of kaolinite and illite, the size of which is 0.005 mm or less. Siltstone material, represented by angular and semi-rolled clastic grains up to 0.02 mm in size, makes up 10-15% of the total weight.

The rock also contains pure transparent quartz fragments without regenerative edges and feldspars in the form of plagioclases of acid composition, which make up 2-3% of the total weight. Fragments of rocks, mainly microquartzites, and single colourless scales of muscovite are found in small quantities. Chalcedony, which has a cryptocrystalline structure, partially or completely replaces individual diatom valves and sponge spicules, and also fills the gaps between the structural elements of the rock (Figure 1). Ore minerals such as pyrite are represented by small black grains of 0.005 mm or less, making up no

more than 1% of the total weight of the rock. Epidote is found as accessory minerals.

Fig. 1: Microstructures of diatomites of the Utesai deposit
Source: compiled by the authors

Membrane technologies, including reverse osmosis and nanofiltration, are extensively employed for groundwater desalination owing to their superior efficacy in eliminating salts, heavy metals, and organic contaminants. However, they are accompanied by considerable disadvantages such as elevated energy consumption, membrane fouling, and the necessity for chemical pretreatment²⁶. Diatomite-based sorbents provide a cost-effective, energy-efficient alternative to existing technologies, as they do not necessitate electricity-intensive pressure systems or chemical reagents for operation. Nevertheless, whereas sorbents proficiently eliminate chlorides and sulphates, their efficacy in removing smaller ionic pollutants and organic contaminants is often inferior to that of membrane procedures. This trade-off indicates that sorbent-based systems are optimal for decentralised or agricultural uses due to their cost-effectiveness and environmental sustainability, but membrane technologies are superior for generating high-purity water in industrial or potable applications.

The study found that diatomites have an organogenic structure, including many whole and fragments of diatom shells (Figure 2). In addition to silicon bioclasts, diatomites contain characteristic clay minerals that form small scaly and leafy aggregates. Particularly prominent are zones of clayisation, where aggregates of clay minerals clearly predominate over bioclastics. These zones indicate the processes of secondary mineralisation that occurred after the development of the bulk of the diatomite. Clay minerals such as kaolinite and illite play an important role in changing the structure and properties of the rock.

An important find is individual spherulites with a diameter of about 10 microns, presumably consisting of cryptocrystalline chalcedony. These spherulites may be the result of syngenetic or early diagenetic transformation processes of siliceous material. Small scales of illite and kaolinite are observed on the surface of spherulites, and sometimes there are furrows measuring 2.2*0.3 microns. These furrows may indicate biogenic activity or specific crystallisation processes.

Fig. 2: Microstructure and mineral components of diatomites of the Utesai deposit

Source: compiled by the authors

The identification of microstructural features in the diatomite samples confirms their elevated porosity and intricate biogenic composition, which are essential for their adsorptive characteristics. The existence of clay minerals like kaolinite and illite indicates secondary mineralisation processes that may affect the mechanical stability and permeability of the material. The presence of cryptocrystalline chalcedony replacement in certain samples signifies diagenetic alterations that might modify the pore structure and sorption characteristics of diatomite.

3.2. Thermal analysis and chemical composition of diatomite

To further investigate the chemical composition and changes of diatomite during heat treatment, a DTA was conducted. A sample of diatomite with a particle size of 1.2 mm and a mass of 200 mg was studied at temperatures up to 1000°C in an atmosphere. Calcined aluminium oxide was used as a reference, and temperature measurement was carried out using a Pt-Pt/Rh thermocouple (Figure 3, Table 1). The analysis showed that diatomite contains high concentrations of silicon (Si) – 40.829 mg and iron (Fe) – 26.008 mg, after thermal modification, the values were 45.924 mg and 35.665 mg, respectively, and after addition of coal – 45.96 mg and 26.133 mg. The concentration of aluminium (Al) decreases significantly after modification from 24.4 mg to 4.364 mg, which may be due to its isolation from the structure of minerals at high temperatures. Calcium (Ca) and magnesium (Mg) show slight changes, which indicates their stability under the conditions of thermal analysis. The spectral intensity of iron (Fe) increases significantly in the modified samples, which indicates its increased content after heat treatment. These data are important for understanding the chemical composition of diatomite and its changes during modification, which is important for various industrial and technological applications of the material.

Fig. 3: Elemental and weight compositions of natural: a) thermally modified; b) carbon-activated; c) diatomite
Source: compiled by the authors

Table 1: Weight composition and spectral intensity of natural and modified diatomites

Element	Weight composition of diatomite, mg			Spectral intensity		
	Natural	Thermally modified	With the addition of coal	Natural	Thermally modified	With the addition of coal
Fe	26.008	35.665	312.02	26.133	288.72	314.53
Ti	1.582	2.933	12.06	1.77	14.93	11
K	4.589	7.663	8.72	6.45	6.08	8.01
Ca	0.382	0.548	2.95	0.648	1.87	2.17
Cr	0.108	0.123	1.51	0.142	1.17	0.95
Al	24.4	4.364	0.28	17.068	0.39	0.04
Si	40.829	45.924	2.01	45.96	1.52	1.69
Cl	1.081	1.308	0.42	1.176	0.38	0.37
Zn	0.380	0.555	0.09	0.007	3.58	3.21
Cu	0.228	0.061	0.81	0.098	1.89	0.31
As	0.237	0.163	1.06	0.108	2.27	0.98
Rb	0.077	0.348	1.18	0.148	0.6	1.7
Sr	0.044	0.306	1.23	0.152	0.35	1.51
Mn	0.055	0.036	1.58	0.138	0.72	0.39

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Cr	0.108	0.123	0.142	1.17	0.95	1.51
Al	24.4	4.364	17.068	0.39	0.04	0.28
Si	40.829	45.924	45.96	1.52	1.69	2.01
Cl	1.081	1.308	1.176	0.38	0.37	0.42
Zn	0.380	0.555	0.007	3.58	3.21	0.09
Cu	0.228	0.061	0.098	1.89	0.31	0.81
As	0.237	0.163	0.108	2.27	0.98	1.06
Rb	0.077	0.348	0.148	0.6	1.7	1.18
Sr	0.044	0.306	0.152	0.35	1.51	1.23
Mn	0.055	0.036	0.138	0.72	0.39	1.58

Source: compiled by the authors

The spectral intensity reflects the amount of radiation or fluorescence that occurs when X-rays are exposed to the sample, and is associated with the concentration of the corresponding element in the material. Analysis of the spectral intensity of Fe showed that in thermally modified diatomite it decreases from 314.53 to 288.72. With the addition of coal, the intensity returns closer to the initial value, amounting to 312.02. The spectral intensity of Fe indicates that the modification reduces the iron content in the diatomite, but the addition of coal can partially compensate for this effect. The spectral intensity of Ti increases with thermal modification and with the addition of coal, which may indicate an increase in the titanium content in the treated samples.

For such elements, Potassium (K), Calcium (Ca), Chromium (Cr), Aluminium (Al), Silicon (Si), Chlorine (Cl), Zinc (Zn), Copper (Cu), Manganese (Mn), Arsen (As), Rubidium (Rb), Strontium (Sr) there is also a change in the spectral intensity depending on the type of diatomite treatment. For example, for Silicon (Si) in thermally modified and coal-added diatomite, an increase in intensity is observed from 1.69 to 2.01, which may indicate a preservation or increase in the silicon content after processing. Therefore, the analysis of the data on the spectral intensity shows that thermal modification and the addition of coal affect the content of various elements in the diatomite. This is important for understanding changes in the chemical composition of the material after various

technological treatments. Thus, a decrease in the spectral intensity of an element after heat treatment may indicate its partial removal or a change in the oxidation state. Moreover, an increase in the spectral intensity indicates its higher content in modified samples.

The results of the study indicate the dependence of the chemical composition of calcined diatomite on the temperature of its processing. In the range of 60-180°C, a dehydration process occurs, accompanied by a weight loss of 2.5%. With further heating, a gradual decrease in weight is observed without obvious thermal effects. The total weight loss at 450°C is approximately 5-6%. The colour of the sample changes from grey to beige after heating (Figure 4).

Fig. 4: Thermal diagram of DTA diatomite

Source: compiled by the authors

Calcination of diatomite affects its adsorption properties by changing the silicon content. The study revealed that the silicon content in the diatomite increased by 5.095%. When activated carbon was added, the change in silicon content is insignificant, by 0.036%, which is due to the removal of adsorbed water and an increase in the sorption capacity of the material. Sintering also affects the structure of the diatomite, leading to an increase in pore size and shrinkage of the substance. The sintering process begins at a temperature of about 500°C.

3.3. Spectroscopic analysis and adsorption efficiency of modified diatomite

Diatomite consists mainly of amorphous SiO₂ and CaCO₃, with the addition of quartz and clay minerals. An analytical study using the IR analysis method confirms its organic occurrence. High-temperature firing makes it possible to activate the sorption properties of the material by removing moisture from the internal pores and shielding organic impurities, which changes the physicochemical properties of diatomite and increases its silicon content. In this case,

the bulk density of diatomite may decrease, and the total porosity may increase during heat treatment (Figure 5).

Fig. 5: IR spectra of untreated: a) calcined, b) carbon-activated, (c) diatomite

Source: compiled by the authors

Thus, it can be concluded that a wide area of about 3,500 cm⁻¹ is associated with the hydroxyl group O-H, stretching of the Si-OH skeleton group and physically adsorbed water molecules. Spectral bands at 1633 cm⁻¹ indicate bending vibrations of water molecules trapped in the silica matrix of diatomite. Peaks at 400 and 1000 cm⁻¹ can be associated with asymmetric modes of stretching Si-O-Si bonds. It is likely that during the calcination process, the Si-O-H bonds are broken and stronger Si-O-Si bonds are formed, which contributes to the increase of sorption capacity due to the crystalline structure of the material. The peak at 798 cm⁻¹ corresponds to symmetrical Si-O-Si stretching

fluctuations, and the peak at 2361 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of organic impurities. The sharp peak at 1512 cm^{-1} may be associated with an unsaturated double bond $\text{C}=\text{C}$ (Figure 5). According to the data obtained, the initial sample of groundwater in the village of Zhanakala, Dzhangali district of West Kazakhstan region, contains salts in concentrations significantly exceeding the maximum permissible rates and requires purification (Table 2).

Table 2: Salt content in the groundwater of the village of Zhanakala, Dzhangali district of West Kazakhstan region

Indicator name	Unit of measurement	Source water	Standard of Sanitary rules and regulations 2.1.4.1074-01
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Chlorides	mg/l	806	<350
Sulphates		955	<500
Salt content		2400	<1000

Source: compiled by the authors.

The use of untreated diatomite to purify the source groundwater has shown the effectiveness of this procedure. As a result of the modification, the chloride content decreased from 806 to 650 mg/l, sulphates from 955 to 773 mg/l, and the total salinity decreased from 2400 to 1936 mg/l. To improve the adsorption properties of the sorbent, it was decided to carry out thermal modification of diatomite (1.2 mm fraction) at a temperature of 450°C in a muffle furnace. As a result, the chloride content decreased from 650 to 594 mg/l, sulphates from 773 to 698 mg/l, and the total salinity decreased from 1936 to 1776 mg/l (Figure 6).

Fig. 6: Results of the purification of groundwater in the village of Zhanakala with untreated, thermally modified, and carbon-activated diatomite

Source: compiled by the authors

The use of diatomite, modified first with activated carbon, and then subjected to heat treatment at 450°C , led to the achievement of the best results of groundwater purification in the village of Zhanakala. This combination of processes provided a degree of purification at the level of 35-37%, which brought the indicators closer to the requirements of technical standards. Activated carbon improves diatomite's ability to adsorb pollutants by increasing its surface area and adding extra functional groups that make it more attractive to pollutants. The increased porosity and surface chemistry enhance the elimination of chlorides and sulphates via electrostatic interactions and physical adsorption, augmenting diatomite's inherent adsorption capability. Furthermore, activated carbon may serve as an additional sorption site, holding residual pollutants that diatomite alone cannot effectively eliminate, resulting in the 35-37% enhancement in groundwater purification documented in the research.

X-ray fluorescence analysis showed a significant increase in silicon content after thermal change. This is linked to better adsorption and structural stability due to a more

porous, high-surface-area framework. The lower levels of aluminium and organic contaminants show that parts that might make adsorption harder have been removed. Infrared spectroscopy revealed a change in Si-OH and Si-O-Si stretching vibrations, signifying an augmentation of active silanol groups, which facilitate improved adsorption of anionic species such as chlorides and sulphates. The structural alterations validate that heat treatment enhances the adsorptive potential of diatomite by augmenting accessible binding sites and facilitating pollutant interactions.

Diatomite resources are plentiful globally, but extensive exploitation may result in land degradation, ecological disturbance, and an activated carbon footprint from mining activities. In comparison to other natural sorbents like zeolites and biosorbents, diatomite mining requires a lot of energy. Adopting sustainable mining procedures, enhancing processing efficiency, and investigating alternate supplies such as recycled diatomaceous earth may alleviate environmental issues and enhance long-term viability.

As a result of the experiments, it was found that diatomite, due to its siliceous structure, is a highly effective sorbent for cleaning groundwater from salts, chlorides, and sulphates. The use of pretreatment with activated carbon and subsequent thermal modification significantly improved the adsorption properties of the material, which affected the efficiency of removing pollutants from the water. Thus, the use of modified diatomite represents a promising approach to solving the problem of groundwater pollution, ensuring compliance with water quality requirements for various technical and household needs, including for watering animals to preserve their health.

4. Discussion

The study showed that diatomite, a naturally occurring mineral sorbent, greatly improves the quality of groundwater by lowering the amounts of chloride, sulphate, and overall salinity. Adding thermal modification at 450°C and carbon activation to diatomite improved its ability to adsorb things, which led to a 35-37% improvement in how well it cleaned groundwater. The results demonstrate that modified diatomite effectively reduces chloride concentrations from 806 mg/L to 506 mg/L, sulphates from 955 mg/L to 603 mg/L, and overall salinity from 2400 mg/L to 1508 mg/L. The findings suggest that diatomite-based treatment enhances groundwater quality to meet acceptable sanitary criteria for agricultural use.

The removal efficiencies of chlorides (37%) and sulphates (35%) attained with modified diatomite in this work are equivalent to or somewhat inferior to those documented for ion-exchange resins and reverse osmosis systems, which generally reach removal efficiencies above 90%²⁷). Ion-exchange resins need frequent regeneration with chemical solutions, hence elevating operational expenses, whereas reverse osmosis systems are characterised by significant energy consumption and membrane fouling challenges. In contrast to zeolites, which demonstrate modest chloride and sulphate adsorption via ion-exchange processes, diatomite's efficacy is comparatively superior due to its cheaper cost and simplicity of modification. Activated clays, while effective for the removal of organic pollutants, typically exhibit reduced affinity for anionic contaminants such as chlorides and sulphates. Consequently, diatomite offers an equilibrium of cost, efficiency, and environmental sustainability in desalination processes. Although the cost-effectiveness of diatomite is apparent, comprehensive comparative assessments of its economic performance relative to reverse osmosis and ion-exchange systems are few in the literature²⁸).

Diatomite's ability to lower salt levels and pollutants is in line with what scientists have already learnt about its absorption. Wang et al.²⁹) emphasised the significant surface area and porosity of diatomite, which enhanced its

efficacy in removing diverse contaminants, such as salts and heavy metals. Their results are similar to those of this study, which showed that heating diatomite to 450°C greatly improved its ability to absorb water, which led to a 35-37% increase in its ability to clean. Both studies agree that changing the structure of diatomite makes it better at cleaning up pollution.

Song et al.³⁰) investigated the environmental safety of diatomite and its effects on water purification. Their results are similar to those of recent research that found that modified diatomite greatly reduced chloride and sulphate levels without creating any harmful intermediates. Both findings endorse the use of diatomite as an eco-friendly substitute for manufactured adsorbents.

Reverse osmosis and ion-exchange systems are frequently favoured for applications necessitating elevated water purity, nevertheless their increased expenses. The cost-effectiveness and efficacy of diatomite render it appropriate for less rigorous applications, including wastewater treatment and agricultural irrigation. Diatomite is being incorporated into biofiltration systems in commercial salmon farms, demonstrating its promise for economical and sustainable water treatment solutions³¹). Diatoms are extensively utilised in aquaculture as live feed because of their nutritional value and capacity to treat wastewater by eliminating eutrophic nutrients³²).

Reka et al.³³) showed that diatomite serves as a cost-effective and efficient substitute for synthetic adsorbents. This conclusion fits with the current study, which shows that using diatomite is more cost-effective than using ion-exchange resins and reverse osmosis. While Reka et al. concentrated on the characterisation and thermal modification of diatomites, the present study expanded upon this research by including activated carbon to augment adsorption efficiency.

The observed reductions of chloride and sulphate levels suggests that diatomite might work just as well as other methods of purification. Diatomite is more economical than activated carbon owing to its natural availability and low processing demands. Despite this, ion-exchange resins and reverse osmosis are better at desalination, but they can be more expensive and require more complicated infrastructure, which makes them harder for farmers to use. Tang and Zhao³⁴) examined the efficacy of ion-exchange resins for the removal of heavy metals. The results of their study show that ion-exchange resins are more selective and effective than some common adsorbents, like diatomite. The current study indicates that diatomite is a more economical and readily available option for agricultural water treatment, especially in lowering chloride and sulphate concentrations. Although ion-exchange resins provide enhanced selectivity, their elevated cost and maintenance demands restrict their use in extensive agricultural applications.

Diatomite efficiently eliminates chlorides and sulphates,

although it may have difficulties with smaller pollutants such as heavy metals.³⁵⁾ In contrast to activated carbon, its efficacy depends on structural alterations. Conversely, reverse osmosis is effective for desalination but encounters difficulties because of elevated energy expenses and membrane fouling. Thesai et al.³⁶⁾ investigated the biological elimination of fluoride using *Bacillus flexus*, indicating that microbial-based interventions can be very efficient. Diatomite's independence from microbial activity suggests that its potential incorporation with bio-adsorption techniques merits more exploration.

The efficacy of diatomite in eliminating chlorides and sulphates corresponds with its worldwide usage. Diatomite is extensively employed in the United States for water purification in cattle farming, but in Australia, it is used in vineyards to improve water quality. Comparable uses have been noted in Canada and Germany, where diatomite is utilised for the treatment of agricultural water³⁷⁾. The elevated adsorption effectiveness of diatomite in various contexts underscores its potential as a universal and economical water cleaning technique. Further study substantiates the ecological advantages of using diatomite. Adu-Boahene et al.³⁸⁾ and Chee et al.³⁹⁾ investigated the amalgamation of natural and chemical coagulants for fluoride elimination, demonstrating that hybrid approaches can attain superior purifying efficacy. Their findings indicate that chemical alterations boost adsorption efficiency, corroborating the current study's conclusion that diatomite's efficacy may be improved via heat modification and carbon activation.

Supplementary study corroborates the ecological advantages of using diatomite. Martini and Afroze⁴⁰⁾ and Karunanithi et al.⁴¹⁾ looked into how diatomite-based and plant-derived sorbents could be used instead of chemicals in the long term. Preisner et al.⁴²⁾ supported the creation of composite diatomite materials that were more resistant to contamination. This shows that ongoing improvements in the processing of diatomite could make it more useful in technologies that clean water. Mena et al.⁴³⁾ highlighted that diatomite can mitigate pollutants in groundwater while preserving ecological sustainability. Their study aligns with the present research, as both confirm diatomite's effectiveness in improving water quality. Additionally, Al-Qodah et al.⁴⁴⁾ examined electrocoagulation-assisted biological therapies, emphasising their efficacy in comparison to diatomite. The study validates the efficacy of modified diatomite as a feasible method for groundwater purification in agricultural contexts.

Recent breakthroughs in water purification highlight the promise of magnetic sorbents sourced from waste materials as an economical and sustainable alternative for water remediation. Osman et al.⁴⁵⁾ demonstrate that magnetic nanomaterials derived from mixed plastic and biomass waste have superior adsorption efficiency, facile separation through magnetic fields, and decreased energy

consumption relative to traditional sorbents. These materials provide a cost-effective, environmentally sustainable alternative for extensive water treatment while fostering a circular economy through the reutilization of industrial and agricultural waste. Furthermore, their reusability and little secondary pollution render them a feasible long-term solution.

Diatomite is an inert and non-toxic substance^{46),47)}. Nonetheless, untreated natural diatomites may leach trace elements, like aluminium, iron, or residual organics, into water. Heat treatment presumably diminishes the danger of leaching, but further leachability assessments are required to verify water safety. Moreover, used diatomite with adsorbed toxins needs proper disposal, and possible techniques such as immobilisation, repurposing in construction materials, or regulated landfill disposal should be investigated.

Prior studies indicate that diatomite can maintain its adsorption capabilities across several cycles when adequately regenerated⁴⁸⁾. The porous structure retains its integrity over moderate heat and chemical treatment, facilitating desorption and reuse. Despite this, long-term use may block pores, damage the structure, or use up all the adsorption sites, making it less effective over time. Future research should assess the long-term stability of diatomite and devise economical regeneration techniques to improve its sustainability in groundwater remediation. Natural groundwater has several competing ions, including bicarbonates, nitrates, phosphates, and heavy metals, which might hinder the adsorption of chloride and sulphate^{49),50)}. Future studies should examine the impact of multi-ion interactions on the performance of diatomite, especially in highly mineralised waters.

The study confirmed the efficacy of modified diatomite as a feasible method for groundwater purification in agricultural contexts. The synergistic use of heat modification and carbon activation markedly improves adsorption performance, rendering it a compelling alternative to pricier purification approaches⁵¹⁾. Future studies ought to concentrate on broadening the analysis to encompass more contaminants, including heavy metals and organic chemicals. Enhancing comparative analyses between diatomite and other purification techniques would further optimise its applicability in diverse environmental and industrial settings.

Diatomite offers a sustainable and eco-friendly alternative for groundwater filtration, owing to its natural origin, non-toxic composition, and possibility for reutilization. Diatomite, a naturally occurring siliceous sedimentary mineral, does not release dangerous by-products into water, in contrast to other chemical treatments that may result in residual toxins^{52),53)}. Furthermore, post-adsorption, diatomite may frequently be reactivated using heat or chemical methods, therefore prolonging its utility and minimising waste production. Despite the necessity for

disposal, wasted diatomite presents few environmental hazards, as it is biodegradable and may be recycled for agricultural, building, or soil remediation applications. Diatomite's characteristics render it a cost-efficient and environmentally friendly alternative to conventional desalination technologies, facilitating sustainable water management without the elevated energy expenses or secondary pollutants linked to membrane and chemical approaches.

The prospect of further research is to investigate the adsorption properties of diatomite in relation to other types of pollutants, such as heavy metals, pesticides, and organic compounds. The limitations of the study are limited sampling: the study was conducted based on the analysis of one diatomite deposit, which may not be representative of other deposits.

5. Conclusions

As a result of the study, it was found that the diatomite of the Utesai deposit of the Mugodzhar district of the Aktobe region of western Kazakhstan has a unique composition and structure, including siliceous bioclasts, clay minerals, and chalcedony. Initial lithological and petrographic analysis showed that the diatomite consists mainly of small fragments of diatom valves and contains characteristic clay minerals such as kaolinite and illite, quartz, and sponge spicules. This demonstrates its organogenic structure and the processes of secondary mineralisation after primary formation.

Thermal modification of diatomite leads to a change in its chemical composition, in particular, to an increase in the content of silicon (Si) from 40.829 mg to 45.924 mg. The addition of activated carbon to diatomite changes its adsorption properties, also increasing the silicon content by 5.095%. Chemical analysis showed a high content of silicon and iron in diatomites before and after their heat treatment. A study conducted on the groundwater of the Zhanakala settlement of the Dzhangali district of the West Kazakhstan region demonstrates a significant salt content exceeding the permissible norms according to Sanitary Rules and Norms 2.1.4.1074-01. The effectiveness of water purification using diatomites modified by heat treatment at 450°C after preliminary activation with coal demonstrates a significant decrease in the concentrations of chlorides, sulphates, and total salinity. The chloride content decreased from 806 mg/l to 506 mg/l, sulphates from 955 mg/l to 603 mg/l, and the total salinity decreased from 2400 mg/l to 1508 mg/l. This indicates that the combination of thermal modification and carbon activation significantly improves the adsorption properties of diatomite and increases its efficiency in water purification. The results of this study show that using thermally modified diatomite along with activated carbon greatly enhances the desalination efficiency of groundwater. This

suggests a feasible and cost-effective alternative to conventional methods such as ion exchange and reverse osmosis. Agriculture, aquaculture, and industrial wastewater treatment may implement this technology on an industrial scale, thereby reducing operational costs and environmental impacts. The findings advocate for the use of natural sorbents in sustainable water management policies, especially in areas with restricted access to expensive desalination facilities. Future research should focus on long-term reusability analyses, scalability evaluations under practical situations, and the influence of competing ions within intricate groundwater matrices. Also, advanced improvements like nano-coatings or composite materials could make adsorption and regeneration even better, which would make diatomite-based purification technologies more useful.

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